

**THE PROCESS OF TRANSFORMATION IN INDUSTRY
REGIONAL CHARACTERISTICS**

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Abstract.

This article debates the process of development in the industry with regional characteristics. In the regions, it is crucial to initiate modernization with deep transformations in the economy, with the revival of industry on a new technological basis, with the formation of its reproductive structure. Internal and external conditions force the regional authorities to perform it comprehensively, simultaneously and in a short-term period, covering all fields of public life.

Keywords: innovative development, industry, region, competition, modernization, industrial policy, regional characteristics.

INTRODUCTION.

the role of the leading field of material production. Industry is still the major producer of goods in terms of industrial and personal consumption, the level of development of which depicts the pace of scientific and technological renewal and the enlargement of employment productivity in other areas and industries. Therefore, the structure of an intentional industrial policy and the upgrade of the mechanisms in order to take advantage of the vital moment in the alteration to the modernization of the whole economy and its sustainable development.

MAIN BODY.

It ought to be noted that any systemic unit of the integrated economy, in turn, consists of a set of sub-components. In that regard, the central units of the structure - the regions - also play a dominant role in the ongoing structural reforms in the economy. According to this, it is indispensable to increase the level of technological armament of the regions, reduce costs, expand the range and diversify specialization, increase resource mobilization and, accordingly, organizational and radical changes in governance relations are essential sectors of structural reform in them (Figure 1).

Fig.1. The main directions of industrial transformation in the region

The productiveness of the continual, structural reforms in the economy depends in many aspects on the extent to which these improvements happen in the structures of the economy. Of specific importance in this regard are the regional structures, which are, first of all, the fact that every single region "becomes a separate operating part of the national economy as a system of independent economic systems", secondly, the high geographical spatial factor in increasing the degree of resource mobilization in the economy, and thirdly, the reform of economic sectors of the state and the fact that sectoral policy in the field of development is always territorial in nature. Simultaneously, the reforms in the regional classification mean not only the improvement of a specific independent economic system formed in the regional structure, but also the manipulation of processes on a micro scale. Transformation is a structural process that represents a complex process of transforming production and organizational structures, constant adaptation to national and regional markets, a high level of risk. It also has a complicated character, a large database, in-depth financial and economic analysis and the process associated with the practical operation of the government support mechanisms as well as the financial and economic policies of a particular region, national economy, industry, or enterprise changes and breakthroughs in its organizational and economic activities, marketing and raw materials, reserve systems, personnel management systems (Fig. 2). Transformation at the individual regional level reveals that structural changes in obstacles such as rising local capacity and resource mobilization, mitigating problems, mitigating environmental disasters, and increasing governance efficiency. Change at the enterprise level serves to ensure the regional priority of the enterprises involved in it, as well as individual industries. This, in turn, will allow promising, highly competitive industries to create a unique "growth point" in the socio-economic development of the region. The entry of Uzbek big business to world markets, as well as the improving openness of the economy of Uzbekistan. The economy of Uzbekistan is identified by many nations as a market economy, but some market institutions are underdeveloped, and if we are willing to be recognized in the world, the authorities have yet to develop them. It would happen the question of the effectiveness of state management of industry relevant, taking into consideration the regional characteristics of the state.

Fig 2. Factors and characteristics of the location of industrial enterprises in the region

In today's competitive world, economic conditions objectively require from the state new mechanisms for the accomplishment of industrial policy, focused on economic growth based on innovations both at the macro and micro levels of the economy. Without a high-tech industry, innovation would not become a real commodity. These problematic trends can only be tackled on the basis of an accelerated comprehensive technological modernization of industry, especially at the regional level. Under these conditions, the study of issues depend on the development of industries that produce science-intensive, high-tech products becomes especially relevant. First and foremost, these are enterprises of the military-industrial complex (DIC), which can become "locomotives" pulling other industries with them. In the context of a significant redistribution of economic powers from the state central locations to the regions, a serious transformation of interbudgetary relations, and the developing process of regionalization, it is especially important to take into account the regional aspects of industrial production. When we talk regarding regionalization, we mean not only the industrial complex of a unique region - the subject of the state, we deem that the objectively emerging industrial complexes of several bordering and economically closely interconnected regions, i.e. we are talking in terms of the microlevel. The need to form a new description of innovative development as a priority of the national industrial policy is becoming more and more distinct. In this issue, there is an urgent need not only to define clear strategic guidelines for an open economy that has a heterogeneous character and significant accumulated intellectual capital, but also in tactics to approach them. It is imperative to form a new pace to the system, to form a national alliance at the regional and state levels, created to achieve very specific strategic goals. It would be necessary to form a network between regional teams of professional managers, as well as to coordinate their actions within the entire economic space. There might be vital to form a new highly professional elite. Only in this case, the old system will improve step by step, in the process of replacement, be replaced by a new, healthier and more

competitive system. Competitiveness at the present-day stage is the prime source of sustainable economic growth. And, in turn, the basis of competitiveness is the innovative actions of business. Achievement, especially global success, is increasingly associated with the renewal of technologies, the development of new markets as well as institutional innovations (innovations of an organizational nature). The modern reality is such that the innovative activity of Uzbek enterprises remains at a rather low level. The innovative potential of Uzbek science and the education system is not used enough. Recently, however, the government has been making efforts to teach business entities to innovate. Today, in the context of expanding the usage of program-target methods in managing the socio-economic development of society, a more explicit emphasis is needed on stimulating the innovative activity of business. Active support of innovations at various levels should become a priority of state policy. It is believed that innovative development should be considered from two positions. Firstly, this is the active introduction and promotion of product innovations to the market. Secondly, the expanded reproduction of the enterprise's capital, based on the application of technological innovations, the transition to a new technological basis. The ascalated change of technologies in the key industries will lead to the formation of a number of modifications and a reduction in innovation cycles. The cutting-edge technological base is determined by the style and technology of the fifth and sixth technological modes. After following which is that the technological order is understood as a set of technical systems and technological processes that express a certain generation (level) of scientific and technological development. Founding an economic system that is flexible and quickly responds to downside changes in the external environment with strong internal connections of the system, available of quickly changing internal settings depending on the depth and duration of external and internal influences, is an extremely difficult task. Actually, when it comes to Uzbekistan - a country with a high diversification of domestic resources, a variety of regional "comparative upsides" and a variety of national "innovation input" - a wide range of research and development and ongoing training of highly qualified personnel. Therefore, the development of the regional industrial sector, taking into account their characteristics on an innovative basis, must be considered as a function of many variables. There is no doubt, the development and effective implementation of innovations presupposes the presence of high-tech industries in the region, however, it is assumed that, the quality of management is an equally important factor in innovative development. The low level and culture of managing the development of the area is due to the fact that many regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan do not correspond to the characteristics of effective economic entities and do not always have enough resources (mainly financially) to actively impact the innovative development of the regional industry. Without the effective use of economic benefits, it is hard to believe to revive the industry and create the prerequisites for an innovative model.

CONCLUSION

All in all, there might be noted that the modernization would not be identical to the one that was carried out in particular stages, as conditions matured in industrialized nations. Internal and external circumstances force the republic to perform it comprehensively, at the same time and in a short time, covering all spheres of public life. We will have to initiate modernization with deep transformations in the economy in the near future regarding the revival of industry on a modern technological basis, the formation of its reproductive structure, the renewal of the social branch and pulling it up to solve modernization problems as well as the development of

the democratic foundations of the political system and the formation of a driving force for innovative transformations, and all this taking into account the regional measures of the Republic Uzbekistan.

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